

Structural, thermal and spectroscopic properties of Tm³⁺ doped TeO₂-Bi₂O₃-ZnO glasses

Karel Veselský^a, Evellyn Santos Magalhaes^b, Khaldoon Nasser^{b,*} , Nirajan Ojha^b, Laetitia Petit^b, Jan Šulc^a, Helena Jelínková^a

^a Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Břehová 7, Prague 115 19, Czech Republic

^b Photonics Laboratory, Tampere University, Korkeakoulunkatu 3, Tampere 33720, Finland

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ABSTRACT

We report the influence of Tm³⁺ doping on the density, thermal, and spectral properties of TeO₂-Bi₂O₃-ZnO tellurite glasses in order to develop a glass with promising lasing properties at 1.9 μm. All investigated compositions exhibit low phonon energies (~747 cm⁻¹) and low OH⁻ content, leading to relatively low multiphonon relaxation rate. The fluorescence lifetime at 1.85 μm decreases rapidly with increasing Tm³⁺ concentration due to concentration quenching via cross-relaxation. Analysis of lifetimes and cross-relaxation rates yields an optimum concentration of 0.55 mol% Tm₂O₃ for maximum laser gain at ~1.9 μm. A broad emission band with a 217 nm FWHM centered at 1.85 μm highlights the potential of these glasses for broadly tunable and short-pulse laser source at ~1.9 μm.

1. Introduction

Tellurite glasses are appealing materials for a wide range of optical and laser applications owing to their unique combination of properties. They offer a wide transmission from near-UV to mid-IR, and a low cut-off phonon energy (~780 cm⁻¹) compared to other oxide glasses such as silicate (~1100 cm⁻¹) or germanate (~880 cm⁻¹) glasses, taken as examples [1]. Tellurite glasses possess good optical and mechanical properties, and unlike the fluoride glasses, they are chemically stable. Depending on their composition, tellurite glasses may show high resistance against crystallization allowing the fabrication of single and multimode fibers. Due to their low melting temperature compared to silicate glasses, they are easy to manufacture. Additionally, they provide higher solubility for rare-earth ions than silicate glasses and broader fluorescence bandwidths than both silicate and fluoride glasses [2]. Tellurite glasses also exhibit a high linear and non-linear refractive indices and a large emission cross-section [3] which make them ideal candidates for Kerr-lens mode-locked lasers [4].

Tellurite glasses have been successfully used as a host for Tm³⁺ ions for broadly tunable pulsed and continuous wave laser at 1.9 μm [4,5], and 2.3 μm [6–8], Q-switched [4] and mode-locked operation [9], and also for fiber amplifiers at 1.47 μm [10]. Tellurite glasses have shown potential for efficient continuous wave laser action near 2 μm both in

bulk and fiber active media [4], so these materials can find applications in coherent radar systems and atmospheric remote sensing [11], high-resolution spectroscopy [12], and medical surgery [13]. Structural, spectroscopic, and laser properties of different Tm³⁺ doped TeO₂ glasses have been studied, such as TZL [8] and TWL [8], TZLN [5–7], TZN and TZNG [1,4,10,14,15], TZC [10], TZBG [16], TBZP [17], where T = tellurite, Z = zinc, W = tungsten, L = lanthanum, N = sodium, G = germanium, C = chlorine, B = bismuth, and P = lead. The tellurite glass within the TeO₂-Bi₂O₃-ZnO glass system is of high interest. Lemiere et al. demonstrated that the glass with the composition 68.25TeO₂-19.5ZnO-9.75Bi₂O₃-2.5Er₂O₃ (in mol%) is a promising candidate as an upconverter and for MIR application due to its depolymerized network [18]. Indeed, the addition of Bi₂O₃ in the tellurite network was reported to create NBOs, increase the refractive index, whereas reduce the OH content [19].

Here we present the influence of Tm³⁺ doping on the structural, thermal, and spectroscopic properties of Tm³⁺ doped TeO₂-Bi₂O₃-ZnO (Tm:TBZ) glasses as a potential laser host for 1.9 μm laser operation.

2. Materials and methods

Glasses with the composition (100-x)(70TeO₂ -10Bi₂O₃-20ZnO) - xTm₂O₃, (in mol%), where x = 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 (labeled as 0.5 Tm, 1.0

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: khaldoon.nasser@tuni.fi (K. Nasser).

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Tm, and 2.0 Tm) were prepared using melt quench technique. The raw materials used were TeO₂ (Sigma-Aldrich, ≥99.99 %), ZnO (Sigma-Aldrich, ≥99.99 %), Bi₂O₃ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99 %), and Tm₂O₃ (Sigma-Aldrich, ≥99.99 %). Glasses were prepared in a 10 g batch using a platinum crucible. The glasses melted for 40 min at temperature ranging from 775 °C to 800 °C, depending on the composition of the glass following the melting procedure optimized in our former study [18]. The glasses were then quenched and annealed at 300 °C for 5 h. After annealing, the glasses were polished into the shape of a block with plane-parallel polished faces and dimensions of 15 mm × 15 mm and a thickness of 5.0 mm.

The density (ρ) of the investigated glasses was measured using the Archimedes principle, with ethanol as an immersion liquid. The accuracy of the measurement was ± 0.02 g/cm³.

The thermal characteristics were determined using differential thermal analysis (DTA) (TA Instruments SDT Q600) at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The glass transition temperature (T_g) was taken at the inflection point of the endothermic peak, the crystallization temperature (T_p) at the maximum of the exothermic peak, and T_x at the onset of the crystallization peak. The accuracy of the measurement was ± 3 °C.

The Raman spectra were measured using a Renishaw inVia Qontor Raman microscope equipped with a cooled charge-coupled device camera, using a 532 nm laser for excitation.

The UV-VIS absorption spectra were measured using a SHIMADZU UV-3600 (spectral resolution 0.2 nm), and the IR absorption spectra were measured using an FTIR Nicolet iS5 (spectral resolution 4 cm⁻¹). The index of refraction was measured by a Metricon Model 2010/M Prism Coupler at five different wavelengths with the accuracy of ± 0.0005 .

The emission spectrum and lifetime were measured simultaneously. The samples, in bulk form, were excited by a laser diode (HLU30F400-790, LIMO) at 787 nm. The fluorescence radiation was collected from the sample by a parabolic gold mirror (MPD229-M01, Thorlabs, reflective focal length of 50.8 mm) and focused into an optical fiber, which was connected to the spectrometer StellarNet RED-WAVE (spectral resolution of 12 nm) and StellarNet Dwarf-Star, (spectral resolution of 2.2 nm). The fluorescence decay time was measured with a ± 5 μ s accuracy, by confocal method [20] using a two pairs of achromatic doublet lenses (AC508-075-B by Thorlabs Inc., diameter of 50.8 mm and focal length of 75 mm), and 50 μ m pinhole. This setup was used to minimize the influence of reabsorption in the sample. To collect signal, the InGaAs FD05D10 (900 – 2600 nm) photodiode connected to a Tektronix TDS3052B (500 MHz, 5 GS/s) oscilloscope was used. For the ³F₄ level lifetime measurement the Ge plate was placed before the pinhole to suppress lower wavelength radiation, including pumping. For the ³H₄ level lifetime measurement a tunable OPO laser system covering the spectral range from 670 up to 2600 nm (EKSPLA NT252, 1 kHz, 1 W @ 750 nm) with ~ 10 ns pulses was used. The lifetime measurements were performed in the low-intensity linear regime.

All structural and spectral properties were measured at room temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Density and thermal properties of the glasses

The density and thermal properties of the investigated glasses are shown in Table 1. The density of the glasses rises with the addition of heavier Tm³⁺ ions, as expected. The DTA thermograms of the glasses is shown in Fig. 1.

The glass transition temperature (T_g) increases slightly with an increase in the Tm₂O₃ content, suggesting a strengthening of the tellurite network due to the addition of Tm³⁺ in the glass network. However, the onset of the crystallization temperature (T_x) and the peak crystallization temperature (T_p) decrease after the addition of Tm₂O₃. It is interesting to point out that the Tm³⁺ containing glasses are not stable against

Table 1

Density and thermal properties of the investigated glasses: density (ρ), Tm³⁺ ion density (N_{Tm}), glass transition temperature (T_g), onset of the crystallization temperature (T_x), crystallization temperature (T_p), and supercooled liquid region (ΔT).

Sample	ρ ± 0.02 [g/ cm ³]	N_{Tm} $\times 10^{20}$ [ion/cm ³]	T_g ± 3 [°C]	T_x ± 3 [°C]	T_p ± 3 [°C]	$\Delta T = (T_x - T_g)$ ± 6 [°C]
0.0 Tm [2]	6.16	0	337	463	490	126
0.5 Tm	6.17	2.12	340	404	435	64
1.0 Tm	6.18	4.21	340	401	432	61
2.0 Tm	6.22	8.38	349	408	445	59

Fig. 1. DTA thermograms of the investigated doped glasses.

crystallization, as evidenced by their low ΔT (< 90 °C). It is unlikely that the fiber can be drawn from the Tm³⁺ doped glasses because the narrow thermal stability window offers too little margin between the glass transition and the onset of crystallization, making the glass prone to crystallization while drawing. Nonetheless, these Tm³⁺ doped glasses are still appropriate for use in bulk sample applications

3.2. Structural properties of the glasses

The Raman spectra of the glasses are shown in Fig. 2, together with those of the undoped glass, measured by Massera et al. [21] for comparison. The spectra were normalized to the band at 747 cm⁻¹. Three main bands are observed at ~ 405 , 663, and 747 cm⁻¹ consistent with typical tellurite glasses [10,21,22]. The band at 405 nm consists of a superposition of a band at ~ 380 cm⁻¹ related to vibration of Bi-O-Bi

Fig. 2. Raman spectra of the investigated glasses showing fundamental Te vibrations with the highest phonon frequency of 747 cm⁻¹.

bonds in (BiO₆) octahedral units and a band ~ 415 cm⁻¹ corresponding to Te-O-Te bridges symmetric bending/stretching modes in TeO₄ bipyramids. The band at 663 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to stretching vibrations of TeO₄ units and the one at 747 cm⁻¹ to stretching vibrations of the TeO₃ trigonal pyramids and their disordered TeO₃₊₁ units. With increasing Tm₂O₃ content the relative intensity of the 405, 663 and 747 cm⁻¹ bands decreases compared to the 747 cm⁻¹ band, indicating a gradual transformation of the glass structure with more TeO₃ and TeO₃₊₁ units containing non-bridging oxygens (NBOs) at the expense of TeO₄ units. This points to a progressive depolymerization of the tellurite network upon Tm₂O₃ addition [23,24].

As the maximum phonon energy is 747 cm⁻¹, the number of phonons required to overcome the gap of 4360 cm⁻¹ from ³H₄ → ³H₅ and 5875 cm⁻¹ from ³F₄ → ³H₆ (Fig. 3) is 5.84 and 7.86, respectively, indicating that the multiphonon relaxation is relatively small. The multiphonon decay rate W_{mp} can be calculated from the formula [10]:

$$W_{mp} = B e^{-\alpha(\Delta E - 2h\nu)} \quad (1)$$

where ΔE is the energy gap between the emitting and the next lower level, and $\alpha = 4.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$ cm and $B^* = 10^{7.97}$ s⁻¹ [25] are dependent on the host, but independent of the specific electronic level, and $h\nu = 747$ cm⁻¹ is the measured maximum phonon energy of the glass [25].

The energy gap between the ³H₄ and the next lower level ³H₅ of the Tm³⁺ ion, determined from the absorption measurement (see Fig. 5a) is $\Delta E = 4360$ cm⁻¹. The value of the multiphonon decay rate calculated using the formula is relatively low $W_{mp} = 132$ s⁻¹, for ³H₄ level, which is slightly less than 138 s⁻¹ in [10] and $W_{mp} = 0.11$ s⁻¹ for the ³F₄ level.

The IR absorption spectra are shown in Fig. 4 together with the undoped sample measured by Massera et al. [21] for comparison. The infrared transmission cut-off edge is located at ~1620 cm⁻¹ (6173 nm). The spectra exhibit a band at around 3000 cm⁻¹ which can be associated with the stretching vibration of the free OH⁻ groups and the band at 2270 cm⁻¹ with very strongly hydrogen-bonded OH⁻ groups [26].

A slight decrease in the intensity of these OH⁻ related absorption bands can be observed with increasing Tm₂O₃ content. We attribute this mainly to the structural evolution observed in Raman spectra (Fig. 2), where the relative intensity of the TeO₄ bands decreases and TeO₃/TeO₃₊₁ units with non-bridging oxygens increase. While in principle more NBOs could provide more sites for OH⁻ incorporation, Lemièrè et al. [18] showed that OH⁻ absorption does not necessarily scale with NBO concentration. In their case, OH⁻ decreased even as NBOs increased, which was explained by the different electronegativity of the modifying cations (Na⁺, Ba²⁺, Bi³⁺). Thus, our results are consistent with a modest reduction of OH⁻ absorption upon Tm₂O₃ content increase, though the underlying mechanism may involve both structural and chemical factors. The free OH⁻ content was calculated from the measured peak absorption coefficient at ~3000 cm⁻¹ using equation [26]:

$$N_{OH} = \frac{N_A}{\epsilon \cdot l} \ln \frac{1}{T} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. Energy diagram of Tm³⁺ ions. Excitation Exc. Transition R - radiative, NR - non radiative, CR - cross-relaxation, ETU - energy transfer upconversion. During CR and ETU processes, energy is transferred between two different Tm³⁺ ions.

Fig. 4. IR absorption spectra of the investigated glasses in comparison to the undoped glass.

where N_A is the Avogadro constant, l is the glass thickness [cm], T is the transmittance, and ϵ is the molar absorptivity of the free OH⁻ groups in the glass, respectively. The molar absorptivity $\epsilon = 49.1 \times 10^3$ cm²/mol for silicate glasses [27] was used as no data are found for tellurite glasses. This may introduce a systematic uncertainty in absolute values but does not affect relative comparisons between the present samples.

The free OH⁻ content decreases with increasing Tm₂O₃ addition, and calculated values of N_{OH} are 2.0, 2.0, and 1.7×10^{19} ions/cm³ for 0.5 Tm, 1.0 Tm, and 2.0 Tm, respectively. This amount of OH⁻ content is similar to 1.71×10^{19} ions/cm³ for undoped glass [21] and is in the same range as for phosphate glasses, 2.4×10^{19} – 2.9×10^{20} ions/cm³ [28] where the $\epsilon = 49.1 \times 10^3$ cm².mol⁻¹ was also used for calculation.

3.3. Absorption spectra and the refractive indices of the glasses as well as Judd-Ofelt analysis

The absorption spectra of the glasses are presented in Fig. 5a. The UV edge at ~400 nm is independent of the Tm₂O₃ content. The absorption spectra show the typical Tm³⁺ absorption bands, the intensity of which increases linearly with increasing Tm³⁺ content.

The most interesting band for laser applications is the band centered at 793 nm, which corresponds to the ³H₆ → ³H₄ transition of Tm³⁺ as this wavelength is used for excitation. The band at around 1.7 μm is also interesting for possible resonant pumping and because of the quasi-three-level character of the ³F₄ → ³H₆ laser transition and the consequent reabsorption. The calculated absorption cross-section σ_{abs} , using N_{Tm} , is 9.12×10^{-21} , 7.76×10^{-21} , and 8.87×10^{-21} cm² at 793 nm, and 5.66×10^{-21} , 4.85×10^{-21} , and 5.54×10^{-21} cm² at 1702 nm for 0.5 Tm, 1.0 Tm, and 2.0 Tm, respectively. The magnitude is comparable to that of silicate glasses 8.6×10^{-21} cm² [29] and is similar to that of other tellurite glasses [4,30], but about 40 % higher than Tm doped TZN, TZC, and TZPN measured by Taylor et al. [10]. As the shape of the absorption band does not change significantly with the Tm³⁺ content, as can be seen from Fig. 5b, the slightly lower value for 1.0 Tm sample might be due to an actual lower concentration of Tm³⁺ ions in the sample.

An increase in the Tm₂O₃ content leads to a slight decrease in the bandwidth of the band centered at 793 nm from 24 to 21 nm, which are about half of the FWHM compared to that of silica ~50 nm due to a lower value sideband around 775 nm. Nonetheless, these bandwidths are well suited for diode pumping. The ³H₆ → ³F₄ transition band centered at ~1702 nm has a FWHM of 171 nm, independently of the Tm₂O₃ content. The relatively small variation in shape, width, and magnitude of this broad band with the Tm₂O₃ content has also been found among other Tm doped tellurite hosts [4,10,30].

The refractive index n of the samples was measured, and the dispersion curve was calculated using the Sellmeier equation:

Fig. 5. Absorption coefficient of the investigated glasses (a), and the calculated absorption cross-section of the ${}^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow {}^3\text{H}_4$ absorption band (b).

$$n^2(\lambda) = A + \frac{B\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - C} \quad (3)$$

where λ is the wavelength, and A, B, and C are Sellmeier coefficients. The calculated coefficients are shown in Table 2, and the fit is shown in Fig. 6. The data for the undoped glass (70TeO₂–10Bi₂O₃–20ZnO) measured by Yousef et al. are shown for comparison [3]. A decrease in the refractive index was observed with the increase in doping concentration. It is worth noting that, the decrease in the refractive index with the addition of Te₂O₃ is accompanied by the TeO₄→TeO₃/TeO₃₊₁ conversion and formation of NBOs, implying that the compositional effect of Tm₂O₃ on dispersion outweighs any NBO-driven increase in polarizability.

From the absorption spectra of the glasses, standard Judd-Ofelt (J-O) analysis [31–33] was performed to calculate the J-O parameters and radiative lifetimes. The J-O parameters Ω_k ($k = 2, 4, 6$) were derived from the measured 5 absorption bands shown in Fig. 5a and their oscillator strength f_{exp} using the least-square fitting approach based on the minimizing of the relative root-mean-square deviation. The normalized root mean square deviation for all three sets of fitted data was found to be $\sim 6\%$. Additionally, the uncertainty of the absorption data of these materials was estimated to cause a $\sim 10\%$ systematic error of the J-O parameters. The obtained J-O parameters Ω_k are listed in Table 3 together with values for other host glasses reported in the literature. Ω_2 is mainly associated with the degree of covalency between the RE ion and the surrounding ligand field. It strongly depends on the asymmetry of the local environment at the Tm³⁺ ion sites in the glass hosts and on the polarizability of the anion. It is particularly sensitive to the hypersensitive (${}^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow {}^3\text{F}_{2,3}$) transition [34]. The investigated glasses have a higher value of Ω_2 compared to silicate and fluoride glasses, but a lower than that of phosphate or germanite glasses. The lower Ω_2 observed for the 1.0 Tm sample suggests that asymmetry and covalent environment of the Tm-O bond is weaker than in 2.0 Tm and 0.5 Tm. This behavior might be related to the opposing effects of refractive index decrease and NBOs enrichment with increasing Tm³⁺ doping concentration. Ω_6 parameter is related to the overlap between the 4f and 5d orbitals and provides some information on the rigidity and viscosity of

Fig. 6. Measured refractive index data of the investigated glasses fitted by the Sellmeier equation, and data for the undoped (0.0 Tm) sample from [3].

Table 3
Judd-Ofelt intensity parameters for Tm³⁺ doped tellurite glasses ($\times 10^{-20} \text{ cm}^2$) and other hosts.

Ω_2	Ω_4	Ω_6	Tm ³⁺ doped host	Ref.
4.56	1.96	1.03	Tellurite:	
3.66	1.91	0.77	0.5 Tm:TBZ	This work
4.12	2.41	0.93	1.0 Tm:TBZ	This work
5.04	1.36	1.22	2.0 Tm:TBZ	This work
5.106	1.174	1.082	Tellurite	[35]
5.40	1.47	1.19	TZN	[30]
2.51	1.71	1.46	LKBBT	[36]
3.38	2.17	1.17	TZC	[10]
2.51	1.33	0.95	TZN	[10]
2.27	1.16	0.11	TZPN	[10]
			LT	[37]
			Other:	
5.7	1.7	1.4	GLS chalcogenide	[38]
3.26	1.20	0.46	silicate	[38]
5.63	1.75	1.11	phosphate	[39]
5.55	2.03	1.26	germanate	[39]
2.57	1.90	0.84	ZBLAN fluoride	[39]

Table 2
Sellmeier coefficients (for wavelength in nm) A, B, and C of the Tm:TBZ glasses.

Sample	A	B	C
0.0 Tm [3]	2.55 ± 0.16	1.77 ± 0.15	57558 ± 3097
0.5 Tm	1.73 ± 0.35	2.60 ± 0.34	44523 ± 4460
1.0 Tm	1.84 ± 0.22	2.44 ± 0.22	46175 ± 3097
2.0 Tm	1.80 ± 0.19	2.44 ± 0.19	45286 ± 2623

hosts [33,34]. The Ω_6 parameter is comparable to values in other tellurite hosts. Ω_4 is affected by a combination of the factors governing Ω_2 and Ω_6 [34].

The calculated oscillator strengths f_{calc} and radiative lifetimes τ_{rad} are summarized in Table 4. The radiative lifetimes in tellurite glass are shorter, e.g. 2.3 ms for ${}^3\text{F}_4$ level compared to silica glass 3.4 ms [40] or 3.3 ms for phosphate [35]. Nonetheless, the radiative lifetime of the

Table 4

Results of the Judd-Ofelt analysis, experimental f_{exp} and calculated f_{calc} oscillator strengths from the 3H_6 level, and estimated radiative lifetimes τ_{rad} of the particular excited state.

Excite state	Barycenter	Wavelength	Refractive index	f_{exp}	f_{calc}	τ_{rad}
	[cm^{-1}]	[nm]	[-]	[10^{-6}]	[10^{-6}]	[ms]
0.5 Tm						
3F_4	5821	1718	2.0872	4.04	3.83	2.31
3H_5	8317	1202	2.0989	2.74	2.96	1.70
3H_4	12628	792	2.1247	4.74	4.44	0.30
3F_3	14538	688	2.1382	4.98	4.63	0.20
$^+3F_2$						
1G_4	21323	469	2.2235	1.68	1.50	0.18
1.0 Tm						
3F_4	5827	1716	2.0767	3.49	3.26	2.74
3H_5	8310	1203	2.0882	2.28	2.53	1.64
3H_4	12629	792	2.1136	3.79	3.53	0.37
3F_3	14527	688	2.1268	4.13	3.79	0.23
$^+3F_2$						
1G_4	21301	469	2.2113	1.44	1.29	0.20
2.0 Tm						
3F_4	5833	1715	2.0669	3.92	3.83	2.36
3H_5	8320	1202	2.0788	2.83	2.90	1.44
3H_4	12637	791	2.1042	4.32	4.09	0.33
3F_3	14541	688	2.1171	4.83	4.61	0.20
$^+3F_2$						
1G_4	21316	469	2.1925	1.76	1.52	0.18

investigated glasses is suitable for Q-switched or ultrafast $\sim 1.9 \mu m$ laser operation but may increase the threshold for CW systems. When comparing different Tm_2O_3 content, only small variations are observed: $\tau_{rad}(^3F_4)$ changes between 2.3 and 2.7 ms for 0.5–2.0 mol% Tm, while higher-lying levels also remain within a similar range. This shows that the local ligand environment of Tm^{3+} ions is not strongly affected by the modest change in doping concentration, which is consistent with the relatively stable Ω_k values and also with the unchanged shape of the absorption spectra. The slightly longer τ_{rad} for the 1.0 Tm sample is consistent with its lower Ω_2 and lower absorption cross-section of that sample, as noted above.

3.4. Fluorescence spectra and lifetime

The normalized emission spectra, under 787 nm excitation, are shown in Fig. 7. The emission band centered at $1.45 \mu m$, with a FWHM of 102 nm, due to the $^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3F_4$ transition (Fig. 7a) remains unchanged with the progressive addition of Tm³⁺ suggesting that the sites of Tm³⁺ are similar in the investigated glasses. The emission band centered at $\sim 1.8 \mu m$, with a FWHM of 217 nm, due to the $^3F_4 \rightarrow ^3H_6$ transition

Fig. 7. Normalized emission spectra of the $^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3F_4$ transition (a) and the $^3F_4 \rightarrow ^3H_6$ transition (b) of the investigated glasses (excitation at 787 nm).

(Fig. 7b) shifts to a lower wavelength and suppresses the sideband around 1600 nm with an increase in the Tm_2O_3 content. The broad emission, compared to other glass hosts such as ZBLAN (~ 125 nm) or silica glass (~ 200 nm) [4], results from different structural units of tellurite glass and is an advantage for wavelength tuning or ultrafast pulse generation.

The stimulated emission cross-section σ_{SE} for particular $J \rightarrow J'$ transition was calculated using the Füchtbauer-Landenburg equation [41]:

$$\sigma_{SE}(\lambda) = \beta_{J \rightarrow J'} \frac{\lambda^5}{8\pi\tau_{rad}cn^2} \frac{I(\lambda)}{\int I(\lambda)d\lambda} \quad (4)$$

with c_0 denoting speed of light and using the measured fluorescence spectra $I(\lambda)$ of $J \rightarrow J'$ transition, the calculated refractive index n , the radiative lifetime τ_{rad} , and branching ratio $\beta_{J \rightarrow J'}$ derived from the J-O analysis. The calculated σ_{SE} are summarized in Table 5.

The calculated emission cross-section at ~ 1855 nm ($\beta(^3F_4 \rightarrow ^3H_6) = 1$) for 0.5 Tm, 1.0 Tm, and 2.0 Tm is 6.9×10^{-21} , 6.8×10^{-21} , and 6.6×10^{-21} cm^2 , respectively. These values are in the same range as 6.7×10^{-21} cm^2 for Tm:TZNG, and higher than 5.0×10^{-21} cm^2 for Tm: TZN [14]. The emission cross-section together with the absorption cross-section, for 0.5 Tm is plotted in Fig. 8a. Due to the overlap of absorption and emission, and the consequent quasi-three level nature of the Tm^{3+} laser emission from 3F_4 , the effective gain cross-section $\sigma_{Gain} = \beta\sigma_{SE} - (1 - \beta)\sigma_{abs}$ was calculated. The σ_{Gain} spectra are plotted in Fig. 8b for different values of $\beta = N_{3F4}/N_{Tm}$, which is the population inversion ration for Tm^{3+} ions where N_{3F4} is the population of the upper laser level 3F_4 . The expected wavelength for low $\beta = 0.2$, moderate $\beta = 0.3$, and higher inversion $\beta = 0.4$ is 1912, 1900, and 1890 nm, with possible tunability from 126, 137, and 147 nm (FWHM), respectively. The emission cross-section at ~ 1459 nm was estimated to be 4.64×10^{-21} cm^2 for all samples, as the shape of the fluorescence does not change. The branching ratio $\beta(^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3F_4) = 0.10$ for the $^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3F_4$ transition, calculated via the J-O analysis, was used.

The fluorescence decay from both 3H_4 and 3F_4 levels exhibited a single exponential behavior and the decay curves from the 3F_4 and 3H_4 level are shown in Fig. 9.

From the exponential fit, the fluorescence lifetime was calculated,

Table 5

Stimulated emission cross-section and fluorescence lifetime of Tm:TBZ.

Sample	0.5 Tm	1.0 Tm	2.0 Tm
σ_{SE} ($\beta(^3F_4 \rightarrow ^3H_6) = 1$) [cm^2]	6.9×10^{-21}	6.8×10^{-21}	6.6×10^{-21}
σ_{SE} ($\beta(^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3F_4) = 0.1$) [cm^2]	4.64×10^{-21}	4.64×10^{-21}	4.64×10^{-21}
τ (3F_4) [ms]	1.254	0.538	0.196
τ (3H_4) [μs]	166	62	11

Fig. 8. Absorption σ_{abs} and stimulated emission cross-section σ_{SE} (a), and effective gain cross-section σ_{Gain} of the ${}^3\text{F}_4 \rightarrow {}^3\text{H}_6$ transition for different inversion ratios β in the 0.5 Tm:TBZ sample.

Fig. 9. Fluorescence intensity decay curves from the ${}^3\text{F}_4$ and ${}^3\text{H}_4$ level.

Fig. 10. Dependence of fluorescence lifetime on the Tm³⁺ doping concentration (a) from the ${}^3\text{H}_4$ level around 0.8 μm , and (b) from the ${}^3\text{F}_4$ level around 1.85 μm .

and its dependence on the Tm³⁺ doping concentration is shown for the ${}^3\text{H}_4$ and ${}^3\text{F}_4$ levels shown in Figs. 10a and 10b, respectively and summarized in Table 5.

The lifetime of both transitions decreases very rapidly with an increase in Tm³⁺ doping due to concentration quenching. The ${}^3\text{F}_4$ level lifetime of 1.25 ms for 0.5 Tm³⁺ sample is lower than the 1.6 ms for Tm³⁺ doped TeO₂-ZnO-Na₂ glasses (TZN) [11], and about half of the 3 ms for TeO₂-Zn-Cl₂ (TZC) glasses [10], where the lifetime did not depend much on doping concentration (for 0.05 up to 2 % of Tm³⁺). As the total OH⁻ content does not change for the 0.5 Tm and 1.0 Tm samples, and even decreases slightly for the 2.0 Tm sample, we can assume that the energy migration through cross-relaxation is responsible for the lifetime decrease.

The cross-relaxation rate can be calculated using the following equation [25]:

$$W_{\text{CR}} = \frac{1}{\tau} - \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{rad}}} - W_{\text{mp}} \quad (5)$$

where τ is the measured lifetime, τ_{rad} is the calculated radiative lifetime, and W_{mp} is the calculated multiphonon transition rate.

The calculated cross-relaxation rate (CR in Fig. 3), between two Tm³⁺ ions (Tm₁ and Tm₂) for energy transfer ${}^3\text{H}_4(\text{Tm}_1) + {}^3\text{H}_6(\text{Tm}_2) \rightarrow {}^3\text{F}_4(\text{Tm}_1) + {}^3\text{F}_4(\text{Tm}_2)$ is 2.56×10^3 , 1.27×10^4 , and $8.74 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$, for 0.5 Tm, 1.0 Tm and 2.0 Tm, respectively, where the $\tau_{\text{rad}} = 2.31 \text{ ms}$ from

the lowest doped sample was used in the calculations. These values are one of magnitude higher than the one reported for 1 % Tm:YLF ($3.00 \times 10^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) [42] and about two orders of magnitude lower than that for 1.34 % Tm:CaF₂ ($1.54 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$) [43] where the cross-relaxation is very high due to Tm³⁺ ions clustering. The reverse process, designated as energy transfer upconversion (ETU in Fig. 3) ${}^3\text{F}_4(\text{Tm}_1) + {}^3\text{F}_4(\text{Tm}_2) \rightarrow {}^3\text{H}_4(\text{Tm}_1) + {}^3\text{H}_6(\text{Tm}_2)$, is about an order lower (3.65×10^2 , 1.43×10^3 , $4.67 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) which is in good agreement with values from the literature [44]. The higher Tm₂O₃ concentration leads to more effective cross-relaxation and population of the ${}^3\text{F}_4$ level, but also increases the probability of energy migrating among Tm³⁺ ions and nonradiatively decaying from this level at OH⁻ and other impurities, decreasing the ${}^3\text{F}_4$ level lifetime.

The cross-relaxation rate W_{CR} of the ${}^3\text{F}_4$ level is linearly proportional to the square of the Tm₂O₃ concentration, as can be seen from Fig. 11a. In this case, we can assume self-quenching through a dipole-dipole interaction in a diffusion limited regime, which can be described by the equation [45]:

$$\tau(N) = \frac{\tau_w}{1 + \frac{9}{2\pi} \left(\frac{N}{N_0} \right)^2} \quad (6)$$

where τ_w is the measured fluorescence lifetime at low concentration, and N_0 is the critical sensitizer concentration for self-quenching. The N_0 is proportional to the critical transfer distance radius $R_0 = (3/4\pi N_0)^{1/3}$, for which the non-radiative energy transfer is as probable as photon emission. For the calculation, we assume that $\tau_w = \tau_{\text{rad}}$ calculated from the J-O analysis.

The fluorescence lifetime of the ${}^3\text{F}_4$ level fitted by Eq. (6), is presented in Fig. 11b. The measured data follows the self-quenching model very well. The critical concentration was estimated to be $N_0 = 2.79 \times 10^{20} \text{ ions/cm}^3$. This value is less than 3.08×10^{20} for Tm³⁺ doped tellurite glasses (TeO₂-TiO₂-Nb₂O₅) and 2.88×10^{20} for germanate glasses (55GeO₂-25PbO-20 Nb₂O₅) [46].

As the laser gain is proportional to the product of the lifetime and concentration $\tau \times N$, it is possible to estimate, from the derivative $d(N\tau/N_0)/dN$ and the Eq. (6), the optimum concentration for laser gain at $\sim 1.9 \mu\text{m}$, which is calculated as $N_{\text{opt}} = \sqrt{2\pi/9} \times N_0$. We expect the optimum Tm³⁺ concentration for the investigated glass system to be $2.3157 \times 10^{20} \text{ ions/cm}^3$ corresponding to 0.55 mol% of Tm₂O₃. The conclusions of the model calculations need to be verified by laser experiments.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we have comprehensively investigated the thermal, structural, and spectroscopic properties of TeO₂-ZnO-Bi₂O₃ glasses doped with 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mol.% of Tm₂O₃, providing what is, to the best of our knowledge, the first systematic study of Tm³⁺-doped TeO₂-ZnO-Bi₂O₃ glasses. All glasses exhibit low phonon energies ($\sim 747 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and relatively low OH⁻ content, resulting in a low multiphonon relaxation rate. The spectral shapes of the absorption and fluorescence bands remain essentially unchanged with increasing Tm₂O₃ concentration, indicating that the Tm³⁺ ions occupy similar sites within the tellurite network. A broad emission band (FWHM = 217 nm) centered at $\sim 1.85 \mu\text{m}$, combined with a stable spectral profile, highlights the potential of these glasses for broadly tunable laser operation and short-pulse generation. The fluorescence lifetime of the ${}^3\text{F}_4$ level at $\sim 1.85 \mu\text{m}$ decreases rapidly with Tm₂O₃ content due to concentration quenching via cross-relaxation. The cross-relaxation rate was found to be strongly dependent on the square of the ion concentration. Analysis of the lifetimes and cross-relaxation rates suggests an optimum Tm³⁺ concentration for maximum laser gain at $\sim 1.9 \mu\text{m}$ of approximately 0.55 mol%, corresponding to $2.32 \times 10^{20} \text{ ions/cm}^3$. Among the synthesized compositions, the glass with 0.5 mol.% Tm₂O₃ is therefore the closest to calculated value and represents the most favorable gain medium among the samples.

Overall, the investigated Tm³⁺ doped TeO₂-ZnO-Bi₂O₃ glasses combine low phonon energy, broad emission bandwidth, and favorable spectroscopic parameters, making them promising candidates for $\sim 1.9 \mu\text{m}$ laser sources, including tunable continuous-wave and ultrafast systems. Future work could focus on optimizing glass processing to further reduce OH⁻ content, tailoring the composition so the glasses are thermally stable to allow fiber drawing, and experimentally demonstrating laser operation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Karel Veselský: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Magalhães Evellyn Santos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Laeticia Petit:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Khaldoun Nasser:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Nirajan Ojha:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jan Sulc:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Helena Jelínková:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Fig. 11. Dependence of W_{CR} on square of Tm³⁺ concentration (a). Dependence of measured lifetime on Tm³⁺ concentration fitted with self-quenching model (b).

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

Data availability

Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

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